

Assessments of Microbial Contamination of Raw Beef in Supermarkets in Phnom Penh

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Abstract: The study focused on analysis and evaluation of microbial contamination of raw beef was designed to (1) determine the presence of foodborne pathogens in raw beef; (2) compare the prevalence of microbial contamination among the three supermarkets, and (3) evaluate the sanitary quality of raw beef products. Also, six kind of microorganisms including Total Plate Count, Total Coliform and Fecal Coliform, which represented sanitary quality and *E. coli*, *S. Aureus* and *B.cereus*, which determined the presence of foodborne pathogens, were analyzed. The procedures used to analyse experimental samples taken from three supermarket (in every one week for three weeks) in Phnom Penh were based on Merck's study in 2005. The results had shown that there were no significant differences in Total Plate Counts, Total Coliform and Fecal Coliform in all samples, and they were found in unacceptable numbers in the raw beef products. However, the prevalence of foodborne pathogens including *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* were found in acceptable numbers. Furthermore, the samples taken from the second supermarket had the highest level of microbial contamination among the three supermarkets, while the samples taken from the first supermarket had the lowest level of microbial contamination. This experimental finding demonstrated the need for sanitary improvement in the beef retails markets and strict sanitary guideline and implementation of these practices could guarantee consumers' health by consuming raw beefs with the lowest risk of foodborne pathogens.

Key words: Raw beef, microbial contamination, foodborne pathogen, sanitary quality, foodborne pathogenic quality.

1. Introduction

In Cambodia, people have faced many kinds of health issues, and some of causes are hygiene problems. Sometimes, it becomes so serious, especially for small children and elderly people [1]. Food is contaminated by bad handling and poor sanitation with food poisoning and food-borne illness. However, it is still not clear about the causes and effects of food poisoning and foodborn illness in Cambodia [2]. Food poisoning arises from sanitation problems or vertical transmission, and in Cambodia, it is still not clear what kinds of factor there are. Beef is a food product that contains a power pack of nutrients including zinc, iron, protein and B-vitamins nutrients that work as hard as you do every day. However, this kind of meat is very easy to

be spoiled by microorganism, which seriously affects the consumer's health. In most cases, beef can be used lightly cooked, so the level of microbial contamination is high to consume like that [3]. Furthermore, the processing in the slaughterhouse of beef has the potential to introduction due to unhygienic practice and equipment. Foodborne pathogens can increase rapidly during the killing process. Foodborne outbreaks due to consumption of raw or lightly cooked beef contaminated with bacterial human pathogens are a food safety concern worldwide, especially in developing countries that lack of the knowledge of food microbiology, food safety and quality [4].

This study was designed to determine the presence of foodborne pathogens in raw beef, compare the prevalence of microbial contamination among the three supermarkets and evaluate the sanitary quality of raw beef products.

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2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

This research was focused on sanitation quality and foodborne pathogenic quality that determined on six parameters such as Total Plate Count, Total Coliforms and Fecal Coliforms for hygiene quality and *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Bacillus cereus* (*B. cereus*) for foodborne pathogenic quality. Samples of raw beef products were taken from three supermarkets in Phnom Penh. The research was held from September to November 2011 and conducted at Microbiological laboratory of Confirel Company.

2.2 Sampling

This experiment was studied on raw beef taken from three different supermarkets in Phnom Penh, Cambodia. Each sample was weighted 500 g, taken from the supermarkets in every one week for three weeks and transported to the laboratory at the temperature from 2 to 5 °C [1].

2.3 Sample Preparation

-Place 25 g of the sample aseptically in the blending jar;

-Then add 225 mL of sterile ringer solution and blend at 10,000-12,000 rpm for 2 min (this provides 1:10 dilution);

-Prepare serial dilutions by transferring 1 mL of homogenate and successive dilutions to 9 mL of sterile ringer solution in Universal bottles (use separate sterile pipette);

-After each dilution, mix the contents in vortex-mixer for 10 s [1].

2.4 Test Procedure

2.4.1 Total Plate Count

-Pipette 1 mL of each dilution into sterile labeled petridishes in duplicate;

-Add 15 to 20 mL of molten plate count agar at

44-46 °C (from two bottles to the duplicate sets) within 15 min of blending the food;

-Mix the contents by rotating the petridishes 5 times clockwise and 5 times anticlockwise alternately;

-Allow the medium to set in a horizontal surface;

-When agar has set, stack the petridishes in inverted position in the incubator (not more than 6 petridishes high; without contacting side walls);

-Incubate at 35 ± 0.2 °C for 24 to 48 h;

-Count duplicate plates containing less than 300 colonies [5].

2.4.2 Total Coliforms

-Pipette 1 mL each of the dilution 1:10, 1:100 and 1:1,000 dilution into three sets of 10 mL sterile Lauryl Tryptose broth tube (containing Durham tubes) in triplicate. Pipetting should be done within 15 min;

-Incubate at 35 ± 0.2 °C for 24 to 48 h. Observe gas production after 24 h and continue incubation (presumptive identity);

-After 48 h of incubation in LT medium agitate the gassing LT tubes, take a loopful from five of the LT tubes containing higher concentrations of inoculate and transfer to 5 BGB tubes, respectively (avoid picking the pellicle from LT tubes);

-Incubate BGB tubes at 35 ± 0.2 °C for 24 to 48 h;

-Lastly, observe gas production for confirmation and record [5].

2.4.3 Fecal Coliform

-Agitate the gassing LT tubes, take a loopful from five LT tubes containing the higher concentration of inoculation and transfer to 5 tubes of EC medium;

-Incubate EC tubes at 44 ± 0.2 °C for 24 to 48 h;

-Then, record gas production at 24 to 48 h for confirmation (MPN) [5].

2.4.4 *E.coli*

-Pipette 1 mL of each dilution into sterile labeled petridishes in duplicate. Add 15-20 mL of molten MacCONKEY agar at 44 to 46 °C (from two bottles to the duplicate sets) within 15 min of blending the food;

-Mix the contents by rotating the petridishes 5 times clockwise and 5 times anticlockwise alternately;

- Allow the medium to set in a horizontal surface;
- When agar has set, stack the petridishes in inverted position in the incubator (not more than 6 petridishes high; without contacting side walls);
- Incubate at 35 ± 0.2 °C for 24 to 48 h. Count duplicate plates containing less than 300 colonies;
- Perform following Confirmative tests such as Gram Stain, Catalase test and Oxidase test [5].

2.4.5 *S. aureus* and *B. cereus*

- Pipette 1 mL of each dilution into sterile labeled petridishes in duplicate. Add 15-20 mL of molten MYP agar at 44 to 46 °C (from two bottles to the duplicate sets) within 15 min of blending the food;
- Mix the contents by rotating the petridishes 5 times clockwise and 5 times anticlockwise alternately;
- Allow the medium to set in a horizontal surface;
- When agar has set, stack the petridishes in inverted position in the incubator (not more than 6 petridishes high; without contacting side walls). Incubate at 32 ± 0.2 °C for 24 to 48 h;
- Count duplicate plates containing less than 300 colonies (yellow colonies for *S. aureus* and red colonies for *B. cereus*);
- Perform following Confirmative tests such as Gram Stain, Catalase test, Oxidase test and VP test [5].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Total Plate Count

The results showed that the first supermarket, samples of the first and third week had total bacteria in satisfactory level, and the sample of the second week had the total bacteria in acceptable level, which minimum number was 0.2×10^6 cfu/g, and 1.5×10^6 cfu/g for maximum number. In the second supermarket, the samples of the second and third week had the total bacteria in unacceptable number, and the sample of the first week had the total bacteria in acceptable number, which the minimum number was 2.6×10^6 cfu/g and 7.8×10^7 cfu/g for maximum number. In the third supermarket, the samples of the first and third week had the total bacteria in satisfactory number, and the

sample of the week had the total bacteria in acceptable number, which the minimum number was 0.5×10^6 cfu/g and 1.3×10^6 cfu/g for maximum number. In addition, the samples taken from the second supermarket had the highest number of bacteria while the first supermarket had the lowest number. The parameter of Total Plate Count was used for determining and evaluating sanitation quality of food that the high number of bacteria could show poor sanitation or have problem with food processing control or raw material [2]. This showed that sanitation of raw beef product in the second supermarket was still low because it was found that samples taken from the second supermarket were in the unacceptable level. Also, there was a research that studied on Total Plate Count on raw beef in supermarkets in Cairo and Giza, Egypt, and the total bacteria was found 8.0×10^5 cfu/g minimum and 3.2×10^7 cfu/g maximum, which was in unacceptable level [6]. Even though raw beef was taken from supermarket, it was still stored with cool temperature and packed properly; all raw meat contained Mesophilic bacteria already since the animals were killed [7].

3.2 Total Coliform and Fecal Coliform

According to Table 1, the number of coliforms and fecal coliforms in each sample taken from the three supermarkets were in the unacceptable number (more than 1,000 cfu/g). The presence of Coliforms demonstrated sanitation quality and other pathogenic on food and water. If there was presence of Coliforms in food, it must have the presence of other foodborne pathogens, which could cause problem to human health [8]. Therefore, the presence of Coliforms in the samples taken from the three supermarkets must contain other foodborne pathogens that could cause people sick. Also, a research study found the present of Coliform and Fecal Coliform in the acceptable level, but her research was conducted in simple markets in Phnom Penh, which was more than 1,100 cfu/g [3]. In addition, the presence of Fecal Coliform demonstrated poor sanitation level because these Coliform bacteria

Table 1 Total coliform and fecal coliform.

Parameters	Sample	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3
Total coliforms	1	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g
	2	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g
	3	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g
Fecal coliforms	1	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g
	2	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g
	3	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g	>1,000cfu/g

included general that originated infeces (e.g., *Escherichia*) as well as generated fecal origin. The assay was intended to be an indicator of fecal contamination; more specifically of *E. coli* which was an indicator microorganism for other pathogens that may be present in feces. Presence of fecal coliforms in water was not directly harmful and did not necessarily indicate the presence of feces [9]. According to the results above, raw beef product in the three supermarkets was needed to improve sanitation quality.

3.3 *E. coli*

According to Fig. 1, the results had shown that all the samples taken from the three supermarkets had the presence of *E. coli*. It was also shown that all the samples from the three supermarkets in each week had the total number of *E. coli* in acceptable number. In the first supermarket, the minimum number was 0.5×10^3 cfu/g and maximum number was 1.7×10^3 cfu/g. In the second supermarket, the minimum number was 0.3×10^3 cfu/g and 0.3×10^4 cfu/g for maximum number. Lastly, in the third supermarket, the minimum number was 0.3×10^3 cfu/g and maximum number was 1.8×10^3 cfu/g. In addition, the samples taken from the second supermarket had the highest number of *E. coli* while the first supermarket had the lowest number, and there was also a research that studied on *E. coli* on raw beef in supermarkets in Cairo and Giza, Egypt. The total bacteria was found 2.4×10^5 cfu/g minimum and 3.5×10^7 cfu/g maximum, which was the acceptable level [6].

3.4 *S. aureus*

According to Fig. 2, the results had shown that all the samples from the three supermarkets had the presence

Fig. 1 Result of *E. coli* in each week of the three supermarkets.

Under the line: in the satisfactory level;
 Between the line — and ---: in the acceptable level;
 Below the line ---: in the unacceptable level.

Fig. 2 Result of *S. aureus* in each week of the three supermarkets.

Fig. 3 Result of *B. aureus* in each week of the three supermarkets.

of *S. aureus*. It was also shown that all the samples taken from the three supermarkets in each week had the total number of *S. aureus* in acceptable number. In the first supermarket, the minimum number was 1.2×10^3 cfu/g and maximum number was 2.5×10^3 cfu/g. In the second supermarket, the minimum number was $2.5 \times$

10^3 cfu/g and maximum number was 7.5×10^3 cfu/g. Lastly, in the third supermarket, the minimum number was 1.5×10^3 cfu/g and maximum number was 4.5×10^3 cfu/g. In addition, the samples taken from the second supermarket had the highest number of *S. aureus* while the first supermarket had the lowest number. Also, the presence of *S. aureus* in, the acceptable level (10^5 cfu/g maximum), but her research was conducted in simple markets in Phnom Penh found by Mourng Puthealeakhena's study [3]. The high number of *S. aureus* can cause serious problem to human health but its presence of *S. aureus* in food rarely makes food consumers die [9].

3.5 *B. cereus*

According to Fig. 3, the results had shown that all the samples taken from the three supermarkets had the presence of *B. cereus*. It was also shown that all the samples from the first supermarkets in each week had the total number of *B. cereus* in satisfactory number, which the minimum number was 0.2×10^3 cfu/g and the maximum number was 0.8×10^3 cfu/g. In the second supermarket, the samples in the first and third week had the total number of *B. cereus* in acceptable number, and the sample in the second week had the number of *B. cereus* in satisfactory number, which the minimum number was 0.1×10^3 cfu/g and the maximum number was 9.5×10^3 cfu/g. In the third supermarket, the samples in the first and third week had the total number of *B. cereus* in acceptable number, and the sample in the second week had the number of *B. cereus* in satisfactory number, which the minimum number was 0.5×10^3 cfu/g and the maximum number was 2.5×10^3 cfu/g. In addition, the samples from the second supermarket had the highest number of *B. cereus* while the first supermarket has the lowest number. There was also a research that studied on *E. coli* on raw beef in supermarkets in Cairo and Giza, Egypt. The total bacteria was found 4.0×10^2 cfu/g minimum and 2.5×10^5 cfu/g maximum, which was in the acceptable level [6]. The high number of *B. cereus* is a serious danger of releasing poison, which causes problem to human health.

4. Conclusions

There were no significant differences in Total Plate Counts, Total Coliform and Fecal coliform in the samples taken from the three supermarkets in Phnom Penh, and they were found in unacceptable numbers in the raw beef products. However, the prevalence of foodborne pathogens including *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* was found in acceptable numbers. Furthermore, the samples taken from the second supermarket had the highest level of microbial contamination among the three supermarkets, while the samples from the first supermarket had the lowest level. This experimental finding demonstrated the need for sanitary improvement in the beef retails market and strict sanitary guideline and implementation of these practices could guarantee consumers' health by consuming raw beefs with lowest risk of foodborne pathogens.

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